

Revision of the Nearctic Genus *Litaneutria* Saussure, 1892

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Abstract. Morphometric, external morphology, and biogeographical data are analyzed across hundreds of *Litaneutria* samples from North America. The findings from this study necessitate a renewed taxonomic revision of the genus.

Introduction. *Litaneutria* is a genus of small ground mantises that are precinctive to North America. With a primary concentration in xeric and mountainous habitats, members of *Litaneutria* are distributed from southwestern Canada to central Mexico, with a wide distribution area that covers the entire western United States and Midwest in between. Anderson provided the first modern treatment of this genus in 2018 that restructured the taxonomy of its constituent species. Since the completion of this treatment, a much more comprehensive study has been conducted by the present author.

Discussion. For the present analysis, the expansive collection of specimens that were previously used from Anderson's 2018 treatment were reexamined, together with a great many fresh specimens that were provided by private collectors and museum loans. Each of these new specimens were rehydrated, remounted to demonstrate the diagnostic morphological features, digitally imaged and precisely measured for cross comparison of older material from the previous collection. This lengthy process revealed the importance of having multiple samples from the same collecting site to understand the intraspecific variation within each population, as museum specimens of *Litaneutria* are susceptible to desiccation or mounting artifacts, which may deform some important morphological characters, e.g. metazonal shrinkage may cause the prozona to appear more expanded or abdominal curl may cause the wings to look comparatively shorter than they do in live specimens.

Although intraspecific morphological variation occurs throughout the delimited distribution ranges of the known *Litaneutria* species, several characters have been established by the present study as demonstrating diagnostic consistency. These features include: vertex elevation, compound eye shape, pronotal morphometry, and male hindwing maculation of macropterous individuals. Biogeographic isolation is the most influential and determinative feature of species demarcation within *Litaneutria*, as the recognized species show well defined distribution ranges within distinct ecoregions, thus

creating unique enclaves of individuals that do not share their genetic information with their congeners.

Anderson's 2018 treatment of *Litaneutria* debunked Hebard's synonymization of the entire genus under just one species, *Litaneutria minor* (Scudder, 1872), and summarized the validity of each historical name, upholding the validity of some, agreeing with the synonymy of others, and introducing two new names into the genus. Most of the conclusions reached within this earlier treatment have been reconfirmed within the results of this more recent analysis. However, some of the taxonomic actions of this earlier work have been contradicted with new evidence and five new species have been revealed and are herein described.

Despite the depth of the current study, wherein morphometrics, external morphology, and biogeographical analyses are utilized, significant concerns remain within our present understanding of *Litaneutria*. Given the presence of brachypterous males within many of the localized populations of *Litaneutria* that often co-occur with macropterous forms, there is a high probability of ongoing speciation taking place. Brachypterous males are understandably at a disadvantage against macropterous males within a scramble competition mating system. But some populations of *Litaneutria* are predominantly or entirely brachypterous with macropterous forms being less common to absent. Further, there seems to be a loose association with habitat elevation and the rate of occurrence with brachypterous form males, with macropterous males being found more frequently at lower elevations and less often at higher elevations. These factors alone hint toward the co-occurrence of cryptic species and suggest that *Litaneutria* is even more speciose than the present study suggests. Or, alternatively, this massive discrepancy in male wing length could be a genuinely rare form of variation among Mantodea with evolutionary advantages that are yet to be assessed. Interspecific issues such as these need to be further explored and may not be fully resolved without a genitalic or molecular level study, which is beyond the scope of this work. The present study merely seeks to better clarify our understanding of *Litaneutria* and should not be regarded as a confident resolution of the constituent species belonging to this genus. It is recommended for future workers to delve further into this often ignored genus through different angles of analysis to help resolve the suspected species complexes.

Litaneutria obscura Scudder, 1896 **stat. rev.**

Scudder introduced the name *obscura* in 1896 to differentiate a series of *Litaneutria* apart from *minor* that possess "far greater depth of the fuliginous mottling of the wing of the male". Scudder noted within his very brief description that this species is "apparently undescribed, and occurs in Arizona, Southern California and Lower California". Otte & Spearman's 2005 *Mantida Species File* lists a holotype female of *obscura* that is deposited within the MCZ at Harvard University. This notation is troubling in that Scudder designated no holotype of this species and made no mention of any females being examined by him, as his diagnosis of *obscura* was based exclusively on a series of macropterous males. In any case, Philip Perkins, the MCZ collection manager, advised the present author in 2016 that all of their Mantodea type specimens had been transferred to the ANSP in exchange for the Horn collection of Coleoptera at some point earlier.

Subsequent contact with Jason Weintraub, collection manager at ANSP in Philadelphia, revealed that their holdings do not contain any type specimens associated with *obscura*. Thus, the original series of *obscura* that were evidently part of Scudder's personal collection are now lost.

Hebard selected Arizona as the type locality for *obscura* in his revision of *Litaneutria* from 1935 before he erroneously placed this name in synonymy with *minor*. In 2018, Anderson moved *obscura* out of synonymy with *minor* and listed this species as a new synonym of *ocularis*. Anderson asserted that “the large population of *Litaneutria* that inhabit the deep southwestern portion of the country is distinct from *L. minor* but inseparable from *L. ocularis*.” The voucher specimens used in Anderson's earlier treatment heavily sampled the Sonoran Desert region but undersampled the Mojave Desert to the north. The few Mojave specimens that were used for this earlier study demonstrated dissimilarities from the more prevalent Sonoran specimens but were considered variations of the same species. After having examined and reared under captivity many more recent samples of *Litaneutria* from the Mojave, it has become clear that the differences between the two desert populations are much more significant and consistent than what can be accounted for through intraspecific variation. It is further noted that most of the Mojave Desert region sits at a higher elevation than the Sonoran Desert and, as such, incorporates an entirely different ecoregion that is defined by high desert ecology and geographic barriers that create reproductive isolation for its resident *Litaneutria* apart from *ocularis*. As the character traits and collection locations of this population align with those described by Scudder for *obscura*, the Mojave Desert population is to be referred to as *obscura*. And, therefore, the previous synonymy put forth by Anderson should be revised to reflect that *obscura* is a valid species and not a junior synonym of *ocularis*.

Given that Scudder never designated a specimen to serve as a holotype for this species, whose identity has remained in doubt for decades, much taxonomic confusion was created within *Litaneutria* as a result. To clarify the taxonomic status of *obscura* and to resolve the organization of *Litaneutria*, it is necessary to erect a neotype for this species. As part of the present study, several specimens attributable to *obscura* have been analyzed from southern California and Arizona, thus one of these specimens will be designated as the neotype. A formal designation of this type and a complete description of this revalidated species follows herein.

Regarding the two previously synonymized names of Jantsch, *clauseni* Jantsch, 1995 and *corseuli*, Jantsch, 1986, the type specimen and type locality of *corseuli* (Kern County, CA, *i.e.* Mojave Desert) matches that of *obscura*, whereas the type specimen and type locality of *clauseni* (Tucson, AZ, *i.e.* Sonoran Desert) matches that of *ocularis*. Therefore, just as the status of *obscura* needs to be revalidated apart from *ocularis*, so too must its junior synonym, *Tithrone corseuli*, be reassigned to *obscura*.

Litaneutria pacifica Scudder, 1896

Within the same paper that Scudder introduced the name *obscura* in 1896, he introduced another name, *pacifica*, to denote a distinct species of *Litaneutria* that “occurs in

Northern California, in the Shasta region”. Just as in *obscura*, Scudder did not designate any type specimens for this species and offered only a very brief description that diagnosed *pacifica* males with wings that are “feebly and uniformly fuliginous, having no sub-basal fuligino-fuscous spot”. Otte & Spearman’s 2005 *Mantida Species File* also lists a holotype female of this species as being deposited within the MCZ at Harvard University. This notation is equally troubling as in the case of *obscura* and for the same reasons, in that Scudder never designated a holotype for *pacifica* and based his analysis exclusively on a macropterous male. And as previously mentioned, there are currently no Mantodea types within the MCZ and the institution to which Scudder’s *Litaneutria* material was reportedly transferred to has no record of these particular specimens. Thus, the original specimen that Scudder used to describe *pacifica* is now lost and, as a result, the identity of *pacifica* has remained in doubt and generated taxonomic confusion within the genus in the same manner as *obscura*. For these reasons, it is also necessary to erect a neotype for *pacifica*. As part of the present study, several specimens attributable to *pacifica* have been analyzed from the Shasta region in northern California and thus one of these specimens will be designated as the neotype. A formal designation of this type and a complete redescription of this species follows herein.

Litaneutria baccina **n. sp.**

Litaneutria from the Great Basin Desert possess a unique combination of characters not found among their congeners. These features, in conjunction with the ecological differences between the high elevation, cold desert ecoregion of the Great Basin Desert and the surrounding lower elevation warm deserts, provide evidence of reproductive isolation and, therefore, warrant the designation of a new species.

Litaneutria chaparrali **n. sp.**

As previously discussed, Hebard synonymized all historical *Litaneutria* names under *minor* in 1935. Although his rationale for this blanket taxonomic maneuver was ill-founded, Hebard recognized at the time of his writing that a population of *Litaneutria* from southern California was potentially distinct. He postulated that, “further investigation may prove the southern coastal Californian insect to be racially distinguishable.” A recent assessment of specimens that were collected from the Southern California Chaparral ecoregion have indeed proven distinguishable from other *Litaneutria*, as Hebard predicted. The combination of morphological characters that members of this population possess, which are found nowhere else among *Litaneutria*, in conjunction with the unique habitat of the southern California/Baja California chaparral where these individuals occur, warrant the designation of a new species.

Litaneutria littoralis **n. sp.**

Litaneutria from the Sinaloa Coastal Plain possess a unique combination of morphological characters apart from their congeners. These characters, in conjunction with the ecological differences between the subtropical coastal plain and the cold climate of the surrounding Sierra Madre Occidental mountain range that dominates eastern Sinaloa, provide evidence of reproductive isolation and, therefore, warrant the designation of a new species.

Litaneutria scopulosa **n. sp.**

Anderson described *elongata* in 2018 from a series of five males and one female. The type locality of this species was listed as Green Valley, Arizona—an area within the Sonoran Desert ecoregion that is occupied by the well established *ocularis*. The male holotype of *elongata* was diagnosed as having broadly globular compound eyes and a significantly narrowed pronotum with an elongated, sharply convergent prozona—a character combination that is also shared by typical *ocularis* specimens. However, the female allotype of *elongata* was described from St. George, Utah, which is an area within the Colorado Plateau ecoregion that is part of an ecologically unique, cold desert that sits at a higher elevation than the surrounding warm Sonoran Desert. Since the establishment of *elongata*, a large collection of *Litaneutria* from the Sonoran Desert were analyzed against a great many new samples from the Colorado Plateau and Southern Rockies. This analysis revealed that both sexes of *ocularis* from the Sonoran Desert have significantly slenderer pronotums than those *Litaneutria* from the Colorado Plateau. Further, no brachypterous males of *ocularis* have been found to date, whereas brachypterous forms of *Litaneutria* are prevalent throughout the Colorado Plateau and Southern Rockies. For those Colorado Plateau individuals that are macropterous, their hindwing length far surpasses that of *ocularis* and the hindwing spot is reduced with poorly defined margins. Given the biogeographical and morphological sameness that is demonstrated between the male *elongata* holotype and typical *ocularis*, *elongata* is to be demoted to a junior synonym of *ocularis*. However, the female *elongata* allotype was found to match other female *Litaneutria* from the Colorado Plateau, with a much greater discrepancy found between it and genuine *ocularis* females from the Sonoran Desert. It is therefore concluded that two distinct species are involved between these differing ecoregions and it is necessary to erect a new species, *scopulosa*, to designate the distinct population of *Litaneutria* that is believed to be precinctive to the Colorado Plateau and Southern Rockies.

Litaneutria superna **n. sp.**

The Columbia Plateau of the Pacific Northwest and Okanogan Plateau of adjacent British Columbia mark the furthest northern latitude of *Litaneutria* distribution. With the Cascade Mountains to the west, Blue Mountains to the south, and Rocky Mountains to the East, the *Litaneutria* inhabitants of this region are geographically and reproductive isolated from their congeners. The Canadian records of *minor* refer to this species, as the true *minor* is a Great Plains species that does not occur in Canada or in any other region west of the Rocky Mountains.

Summary. As a result of the morphometric, external morphology, and biogeographical data that has been analyzed across hundreds of *Litaneutria* samples from North America it is the present understanding that *Litaneutria* is comprised of eleven distinct species, of which five are new:

Litaneutria baccina **n. sp.**

Litaneutria chaparrali **n. sp.**

Litaneutria emarginata Anderson, 2018

Litaneutria littoralis **n. sp.**

Litaneutria minor (Scudder, 1872)

Litaneutria obscura Scudder, 1896 **stat. rev.**

= *Tithrone corseuli* Jantsch, 1986 **n. syn.**

Litaneutria ocularis Saussure, 1892

= *Litaneutria elongata* Anderson, 2018 **n. syn.**

Litaneutria pacifica Scudder, 1896

Litaneutria scopulosa **n. sp.**

Litaneutria skinneri Rehn, 1907

Litaneutria superna **n. sp.**

References. Saussure (1892) pgs 123-124; Scudder (1896) pgs 209-210; Hebard (1935) pgs 275-277; Otte & Spearman (2005) pgs 154-155; Perkins pers. comm. (2016); Anderson (2018) pgs 39-53; Anderson (2019) pgs 39-53

Pronotum Morphometry. PL = pronotum length, measured from posterior to anterior margin. DW = supracoxal dilation width, measured from the outermost margins of the expansion. MW = minimal metazonal width, measuring from the narrowest constriction of the metazona. The pronotal length value (PL) divided by the supracoxal dilation width value (DW) will generate the PL:DW ratio, expressed to the nearest one hundredth. The pronotal length value (PL) divided by the minimal metazonal width value (MW) will generate the PL:MW ratio, expressed to the nearest one hundredth. Note that all morphometrics presented herein are mean values that have been derived through careful measurement of many multiples of voucher specimens for as near accurate metric as possible.

Litaneutria Saussure, 1892

Description. Habitus small. Head capsule roughly triangular. Vertex concave, flattened, or arched. Lower frons transverse. Compound eyes ovate-rounded to angulate. Pronotum longer than forecoxae, keeled with pronounced to weakly marked supracoxal dilation. Prozonal margins gradually to sharply converging, supracoxal sulcus well marked. Prothoracic legs relatively shortened in relation to body. Forefemora slender, armed with 4 posteroventral spines, 10-14 anteroventral, and 3-4 discoidal spines. Tibial spur groove placed approximately in middle of forefemora. Foretibiae armed with 7-10 posteroventral and 7-11 anteroventral spines. Mesothoracic and metathoracic legs moderately slender, dorsal surface rounded. Meso/metathoracic femora with genicular spine. Metathoracic metatarsus roughly as long as remaining segments combined. Males may be macropterous or brachypterous; females consistently brachypterous. Macropterous male forewings subhyaline, narrow, typically exposing last 1-4 abdominal tergites. Stigma absent. Brachypterous males and females have forewings measuring about as long as pronotum or shorter, subopaque, typically with darkened preapical band. Macropterous males with discoidal area of hindwings narrow, anal area variably maculated with contrasting blotch in basal third. Brachypterous males and females with hindwings infumated throughout with darkened center portion of anal area. Abdomen fusiform to elongate. Supra-anal plate quite large, generally rounded at base, keeled. Cerci typically long, usually surpassing subgenital plate.

Type Species: *Litaneutria ocularis* Saussure, 1892

Species Checklist:

- *Litaneutria baccina* n. sp.
- *Litaneutria chaparrali* n. sp.
- *Litaneutria emarginata* Anderson, 2018
- *Litaneutria littoralis* n. sp.
- *Litaneutria minor* (Scudder, 1872)
- *Litaneutria obscura* Scudder, 1896 **stat. rev.**
- *Litaneutria ocularis* Saussure, 1892
- *Litaneutria pacifica* Scudder, 1896
- *Litaneutria scopulosa* n. sp.
- *Litaneutria skinneri* Rehn, 1907
- *Litaneutria superna* n. sp.

Key to *Litaneutria* Males:

- 1 Middle of vertex level with or arched above dorsal surface of compound eyes ... 2
- 1' Middle of vertex placed below dorsal surface of compound eyes 3

- 2 Pronotum slender; pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.46, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.83. Brachypterous individuals co-occur with macropterous forms *L. skinneri*
- 2' Pronotum subcompact; pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.13, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.40. Solely brachypterous *L. baccina*

3	Dorsal surface of compound eyes bluntly conical	4
3'	Dorsal surface of compound eyes truncated to rounded	6
4	Supracoxal dilation weakly to moderately marked; metazonal margins parallel ...	5
4'	Supracoxal dilation pronounced; metazonal margins constricted	<i>L. chaparrali</i>
5	Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.66, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.80. Hindwing spot pigmented light brown. Precinctive to Rio Grande Valley of Southern Texas Plains	<i>L. emarginata</i>
5	Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.44, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.65. Hindwing spot pigmented black. Precinctive to Sinaloa Coastal Plain	<i>L. littoralis</i>
6	Brachypterous—wings shortened as in female	12
6'	Macropterous—wings fully lengthened	7
7	Anal area of hindwings with light to very dark maculation. Hindwing spot light to heavily darkened, always present. Occurs in various mountainous, xeric and grassland regions east to north of Sierra Nevada	8
7'	Anal area of hindwings with faint maculation. Hindwing spot faint, occasionally absent. Precinctive to Mediterranean California	<i>L. pacifica</i>
8	Hindwing maculation light to moderate, light brownish in coloration. Delimitation of hindwing spot clearly defined, contrasted against lighter surrounding maculation	9
8'	Hindwing maculation typically heavy, dark brown to blackish in coloration. Delimitation of hindwing spot poorly defined, obscured against dark surrounding maculation	<i>L. obscura</i>
9	Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width <2.36, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width <3.49. Occurs in high elevation mountainous regions	10
9'	Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width >2.36, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width >3.49. Occurs in low elevation xeric and grassland regions ...	11
10	Hindwings short and narrow. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.35, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.37. Precinctive to Columbia Plateau/Blue Mountain foothills and adjacent Okanogan Plateau within Cascadia	<i>L. superna</i>
10'	Hindwings long and narrow. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.27, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.47. Precinctive to Colorado Plateau and Southern Rockies within Rocky Mountains	<i>L. scopulosa</i>
11	Compound eyes narrowly ovoid, somewhat truncated. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.48, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.50. Precinctive to Chihuahuan Desert and Great Plains	<i>L. minor</i>

- 11' Compound eyes prominently rounded. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.37, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.53. Precinctive to Sonoran and Baja California Deserts *L. ocularis*
- 12 Pronotal length to minimal metazonal width <3.65. Occurs east or north of Sierra Nevada 13
- 12' Pronotal length to minimal metazonal width >3.65. Occurs west of Sierra Nevada *L. pacifica*
- 13 Pronotum shortened, relatively robust; pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.27-2.35. Occurs in high elevation xeric regions west of or within the Rocky Mountains 14
- 13' Pronotum elongated; pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.48. Precinctive to Chihuahuan Desert and Great Plains *L. minor*
- 14 Compound eyes prominently rounded. Occurs south to southeast of Cascadia .. 15
- 14' Compound eyes narrowly ovoid. Precinctive to Columbia Plateau/Blue Mountain foothills and adjacent Okanogan Plateau within Cascadia *L. superna*
- 15 Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.27. Pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.47. Precinctive to Colorado Plateau and Southern Rockies ...
..... *L. scopulosa*
- 15' Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.34. Pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.54. Precinctive to Mojave Desert *L. obscura*

Litaneutria baccina ♂

Litaneutria chaparrali ♂

Litaneutria scopulosa ♂

Litaneutria emarginata ♂

Litaneutria minor ♂

Litaneutria obscura ♂

Figure Plate 1. *Litaneutria* male head capsules (frontal view), demonstrating vertex elevation and compound eye shape. Note that these photos are focused upon the diagnostic features of the vertex and dorsal surface of the compound eyes, thus the lower frons area may be out of focus on some samples.

Litaneutria ocularis ♂

Litaneutria pacifica ♂

Litaneutria skinneri ♂

Litaneutria superna ♂

Litaneutria littoralis ♂

Figure Plate 2. *Litaneutria* male head capsules (frontal view), demonstrating vertex elevation and compound eye shape. Note that these photos are focused upon the diagnostic features of the vertex and dorsal surface of the compound eyes, thus the lower frons area may be out of focus on some samples.

Figure Plate 3. *Litaneutria* male pronotums, demonstrating dimensional proportions.

Litaneutria baccina ♂

Litaneutria chaparrali ♂

Litaneutria scopulosa ♂

Litaneutria emarginata ♂

Litaneutria minor ♂

Litaneutria obscura ♂

Figure Plate 4. *Litaneutria* male hindwings, demonstrating wing spot contrast and anal area maculation of macropterous forms.

Litaneutria ocularis ♂

Litaneutria pacifica ♂

Litaneutria skinneri ♂

Litaneutria superna ♂

Litaneutria littoralis ♂

Figure Plate 5. *Litaneutria* male hindwings, demonstrating wing spot contrast and anal area maculation of macropterous forms.

Key to *Litaneutria* Females:

- 1 Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width >2, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width >3 2
- 1' Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width <2, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width <3 *L. baccina*

- 2 Occurs in coastal, high elevation cold desert, or low elevation warm desert regions west of or within the Rocky Mountains 4
- 2' Occurs in grassland and low elevation xeric regions east or south of the Rocky Mountains 3

- 3 Vertex placed significantly lower than dorsal surface of compound eyes, bearing deep sulcus in middle. Compound eyes weakly conical, dorsal surface raised into blunted points *L. emarginata*
- 3' Vertex slightly raised above dorsal surface of compound eyes with middle portion smoothed into shallow arch. Compound eyes narrowly rounded, dorsal surface somewhat truncated *L. minor*

- 4 Dorsal surface of compound eyes broadly rounded. Occurs east or north of the Sierra Nevada 6
- 4' Dorsal surface of compound eyes narrowly rounded to sharply angulate. Occurs west or south of the Sierra Nevada 5

- 5 Vertex slightly raised above dorsal surface of compound eyes, flattened to weakly convex in middle. Dorsal surface of compound eyes sharply angulate *L. chaparrali*
- 5' Vertex raised well above dorsal surface of compound eyes, broadly arched in middle. Dorsal surface of compound eyes narrowly rounded *L. pacifica*

- 6 Vertex level with or raised slightly above dorsal surface of compound eyes in shallow arch. Compound eyes protruding 7
- 6' Vertex raised in high arch above dorsal surface of compound eyes. Compound eyes narrowly ovoid *L. skinneri*

- 7 Pronotal length to minimal metazonal width <3.16. Occurs in cold desert regions 8
- 7' Pronotal length to minimal metazonal width >3.21. Occurs in warm desert regions 9

- 8 Supracoxal dilation narrow, indistinct; pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.30. Precinctive to Columbia Plateau/Blue Mountain foothills and adjacent Okanogan Plateau within Cascadia *L. superna*
- 8' Supracoxal dilation broad, pronounced; pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.17. Precinctive to Colorado Plateau and Southern Rockies within Rocky Mountains *L. scopulosa*

- 9 Pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.41. Precinctive to Mojave Desert ..
 *L. obscura*
- 9' Pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.21. Precinctive to Sonoran and
 Baja California Deserts *L. ocularis*

NOTE: female of *L. littoralis* is known only from photographic observation

Litaneutria baccina ♀

Litaneutria chaparrali ♀

Litaneutria scopulosa ♀

Litaneutria emarginata ♀

Figure Plate 6. *Litaneutria* female head capsules (frontal view), demonstrating vertex elevation and compound eye shape. Note that these photos are focused upon the diagnostic features of the vertex and dorsal surface of the compound eyes, thus the lower frons area may be out of focus on some samples.

Litaneutria minor ♀

Litaneutria obscura ♀

Litaneutria ocularis ♀

Litaneutria pacifica ♀

Litaneutria skinneri ♀

Litaneutria superna ♀

Figure Plate 7. *Litaneutria* female head capsules (frontal view), demonstrating vertex elevation and compound eye shape. Note that these photos are focused upon the diagnostic features of the vertex and dorsal surface of the compound eyes, thus the lower frons area may be out of focus on some samples.

L. baccina ♀

L. chaparrali ♀

L. scopulosa ♀

L. emarginata ♀

L. minor ♀

L. obscura ♀

L. ocellaris ♀

L. pacifica ♀

L. skinneri ♀

L. superna ♀

Figure Plate 8. *Litaneutria* female pronotums, demonstrating dimensional proportions.

Figure Plate 9. Distribution range map of *Litaneutria* spp.

A

B

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Litaneutria baccina*: A, male holotype dorsal habitus. Provo, Utah Co, UT 09.10.75; B, female allotype dorsal habitus. Genola, Utah Co, TX 08.02.80

Litaneutria baccina n. sp.

Type Material. Holotype. 1 ♂ Provo, Utah Co, UT 10.09.75, RLClark. **Allotype.** 1 ♀ Goshen Pond near Genola, Utah Co, UT 08.02.80, SMClark. **Paratypes.** 1 ♂ Richfield, Sevier Co, UT 07.13.92, KKAnderson; 1 ♀ Richfield, Sevier Co, UT 10.19.94, SHill; 1 ♀ Mono Lake, Mono Co, CA 08.17.79. The female paratype is deposited at the California Department of Food & Agriculture Plant Pest Diagnostics Center in Sacramento, CA. All other type material is deposited within the author's private collection in Las Vegas, NV.

Description. Habitus small for genus. General coloration light gray, brownish-gray or light brown with variable degree of black punctulation and whitish, tan, or brown mottling.

Head capsule with vertex raised above dorsal surface of compound eyes in both sexes; middle of vertex typically formed in shallow arch. Compound eyes somewhat reduced, pigmented same color as body with darkened mottling and band that extends from base of antennae. Lower frons approximately twice as wide as high, superior margin broadly arched with blunted point in center. Ocelli rather small in both sexes, grouped together in tight triangle configuration just above base of antennae with unpaired median ocellus ovoid and lateral ocelli more rounded. Antennae black or brown, filiform, extending to posterior margin of pronotum in female, reaching to metathorax in male.

Pronotum short, stout in both sexes, more so in female. Male pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.13, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.40; female pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 1.97, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 2.97. Metazona relatively short and narrow with abrupt supracoxal expansion. Prozona broad, spanning much wider than metazona, with gradually converging margins. Lateral margins of pronotum with fine, interspersed denticulation in male, stronger denticulation in female. Pronotal disc relatively smooth with scattering of small callous warts near median. Supracoxal dilation marked with distinct supracoxal sulcus. Medial keel distinct throughout pronotum, more salient along metazona. Coloration typically brownish-gray with variable degree of gray blotching.

Prothoracic legs. Forecoxae shorter than pronotum. Forefemora with 4 posteroventral, 14 anteroventral, and 3 discoidal spines, all with dark tips. Anteroventral spines alternate in length. Tibial spur furrow positioned in middle of forefemora. Foretibiae with 7 posteroventral, 10 anteroventral, black-tipped spines that successively increase in length toward distal apex; tibial spur blackish. Prothoracic legs colored brownish-gray, blotched with lighter gray to darker brown.

Meso/metathoracic legs slender, femora gray in middle of shaft, variably punctulated with brownish-black, with single, darkened annulation toward apices; tibiae typically shaded lighter brownish-gray. Metathoracic metatarsi elongated, as long as remaining segments combined.

Wings. Both sexes brachypterous with forewings reaching midway down abdominal tergite I. Forewings elongate-oval, mottled brownish-gray; stigma unicolorous with background color, inconspicuous. Hindwings project beyond apices of forewings at repose, reaching to proximal margin of tergite II; exposed portion of hindwings

pigmented brownish-gray. Anal area of hindwings entirely infumated with primary veins blackish, venules hyaline.

Abdomen. Male abdomen narrow, sides parallel. Supra-anal plate broadly rounded, carinate at base. Cerci long, extending past styli, cylindrical, tapering. Coloration largely gray on dorsal surface with light brown highlights and darkened lateral margins of each tergite; ventral surface suffused with much more extensive light brown. Female abdomen fusiform with distal margins of tergites II-IX armed with pair of upturned, triangular-shaped protuberances along median. Pigmentation brownish-gray, streaked with faint lighter gray or reddish-brown, occasionally with a pair of black parallel lines extending down dorsal median. Female supra-anal plate nearly as large as tergites VII-IX combined, rooflike with rounded corners and arched median crest.

Measurements. (all measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 20.5-22.5; pronotum length 4.5-5.5; forewing length 4.5-5.5; prothoracic coxa length 3-3.5; prothoracic femur length 4.5-5; metathoracic femur length 7-7.5. *Female.* Body length 23-28.5; pronotum length 5-6.5; forewing length 4.5-7.5; prothoracic coxa length 3.5-4.5; prothoracic femur length 5-5.5; metathoracic femur length 6.5-8.

Biological Notes. Nymphs resemble adults in form, with dorsal surface of compound eyes more prominently pointed in younger instars, becoming more evenly rounded with age. Nymphs demonstrate the same base colors of adults, often marked with pair of blackish parallel lines down median of abdominal dorsal surface. Earlier instar nymphs generally darker with more contrasting black mottling and annulation along antennae and meso/metathoracic legs than later instars. Nymphs mature in approximately 3 months. Males reach adulthood before females, as they require one less molt to reach maturity.

Adulthood. This species is univoltine. Adults occur from mid-July to late September. Habitat includes open desert and rocky foothills with sparse vegetation. Adults and nymphs are most commonly encountered actively running along the ground amid rocks or leaf litter. They are less often found climbing within dry shrubbery and are occasionally found in low-lying green vegetation and scrub flowers.

Ethology. Adults are active both day and night with males being attracted to lights. Adults do not demonstrate a deimatic display but rather quickly dart away with great agility in response to danger.

Diagnosis. This species is diagnosable among *Litaneutria* by the comparatively small habitus with a stout, subcompact pronotum. Male pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.13, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.40. Female pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 1.97, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 2.97. Based on current knowledge, males are consistently brachypterous. Both sexes possess a small head capsule with vertex raised above dorsal surface of compound eyes. These character combinations are unique among *Litaneutria*. This species is precinctive to the Great Basin Desert.

Etymology. *baccina* is the Latinized derivative of basin or large depression, referring to the Great Basin Desert, a massive xeric depression surrounded by mountains, where this species was first documented.

***Litaneutria baccina* Distribution Range**

01, *Litaneutria baccina* adult male. Poleta, Inyo Co, CA 09.01.20

02, *Litaneutria baccina* adult female. Poleta, Inyo Co, CA 09.01.20

03, *Litaneutria baccina* nymph. Mono, Mono Co, CA 07.28.19

Contributing Photographers.

01, *Litaneutria baccina* adult male
Photographed by Alice Abela

02, *Litaneutria baccina* adult female
Photographed by Alice Abela

03, *Litaneutria baccina* nymph
Photographed by James P. Bailey

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Litanentria chaparrali*: A, male holotype dorsal habitus. Peters Canyon, Orange Co, CA 08.09.67; B, female allotype dorsal habitus. San Juan Capistrano, Orange Co, CA 05.09.66

Litaneutria chaparrali n. sp.

Type Material. Holotype. 1 ♂ Peters Canyon, Orange Co, CA 09.08.67, ECrawmer. **Allotype.** 1 ♀ San Juan Capistrano, Orange Co, CA 05.09.66. **Paratypes.** 1 ♂ Julian, San Diego Co, CA 07.10.66, EDWeiderl; 1 ♀ Gilman Hot Springs, Riverside Co, CA 03.04.79, RLAalbu; 1 ♂ San Ysidro, San Diego Co, CA 06.17.69; 1 ♂ Hemet, Riverside Co, CA 06.10.63. The male paratype from Hemet, CA is deposited within the author's private collection in Las Vegas, NV. All other type material is deposited at the California Department of Food & Agriculture Plant Pest Diagnostics Center in Sacramento, CA.

Description. Habitus small, slender. Pigmentation variable; generally colored light brown to gray, variably punctated with black and shaded or streaked with brown.

Head capsule much broader than pronotum, strongly triangular. Male vertex placed well below dorsal surface of compound eyes. Female vertex slightly raised above dorsal surface of compound eyes, flattened to weakly convex in middle. Dorsal surface of compound eyes bluntly conical in male, flattened and angulate in female. Lower frons approximately twice as wide as high, superior margin with blunted point in center. Ocelli rather small in both sexes, grouped together in tight triangle configuration just above base of antennae with unpaired median ocellus ovoid and lateral ocelli more rounded. Antennae brownish, filiform, extending to posterior margin of pronotum in female, reaching metathorax in male. Head capsule predominantly colored light brown or gray, occasionally with brown shading. Compound eyes pigmented same as body color.

Pronotum with distinct supracoxal sulcus, medial keel salient, more prevalent along metazona. Male pronotum relatively narrow, lateral margins unarmed; metazona markedly constricted, supracoxal dilation pronounced, prozona elongated with margins abruptly converging anteriorly. Male pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.41, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.69. Female pronotum relatively narrow, lateral margins strongly dentate; metazona slightly constricted, supracoxal dilation pronounced, broadened. Female pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.33, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.67. Pigmentation of pronotum brownish-gray with variable degree of darker punctation, occasionally with extensive brown shading or darkened stripes against base color.

Prothoracic legs slender, relatively shortened in relation to body. Forecoxae measuring shorter than pronotum, slightly thickened toward base. Forefemora with straight dorsal margin, ventral margin somewhat expanded near middle. Forefemora armed with 4 posteroventral, 11 anteroventral, and 3 discoidal spines, all with dark tips. Anteroventral spines alternate in length. Tibial spur furrow positioned in middle of forefemora. Foretibiae armed with 8 posteroventral, 11 anteroventral black-tipped spines that successively increase in length toward distal apex; tibial spur darkened. Prothoracic legs pigmented light brown or gray, variably punctated with black that occasionally forms small blotches on interior surface.

Meso/metathoracic legs slender, femora pigmented light brown to gray in middle of shaft, variably punctulated with black, apices darkened; tibiae typically shaded lighter base color with darkened apices. Metathoracic metatarsi elongated, measuring as long as remaining segments combined.

Wings. Based on current knowledge, males of this species are all macropterous; no brachypterous forms have been observed or collected. Male forewings are elongate-elliptical in shape, extending to abdominal tergite VI-VII at repose, exposing remaining segments of abdomen. Discoidal area of forewings hyaline with light brown or gray tint, somewhat darkening toward subhyaline costal area. Female brachypterous, forewings oval in shape, reaching midway down tergite I, occasionally reaching into tergite II. Pigmentation of female forewings light brown or gray with darkened preapical band. Some individuals may have major venation marked with brown. Male hindwings moderately to faintly maculated with radiating rows of brownish or light gray tessellation against hyaline field. Sub-basal region of anal area adorned with contrasting blotch that may be darkened or faint. Hindwings of female project beyond apices of forewings when wings at repose, reaching to distal margin of tergite II. Exposed portion of hindwing apices pigmented brown to gray. Anal area of hindwings with brownish maculation throughout, center portion darkened.

Abdomen. Male abdomen cylindrical, narrow, sides parallel. Supra-anal plate broadly rounded, carinate at base. Cerci long, extending past styli, cylindrical, tapering. Coloration light brown to gray on dorsal surface with darker streaks; ventral surface suffused with much more extensive light brown. Female abdomen fusiform with distal margins of tergites II-IX armed with pair of upturned, triangular-shaped protuberances along median. Female supra-anal plate nearly as large as tergites VII-IX combined, rooflike with rounded corners and arched median crest. Pigmentation light brown to gray, streaked with darker gray or shaded with reddish-brown, occasionally marked with pair of black parallel lines extending down dorsal median.

Measurements. (all measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 28.5-31; pronotum length 5-6; forewing length 18-22; prothoracic coxa length 3.5-4; prothoracic femur length 5-5.5; metathoracic femur length 7.5-8. *Female.* Body length 26.5-29.5; pronotum length 6-6.5; forewing length 7-7.5; prothoracic coxa length 3.5-4.5; prothoracic femur length 5.5-6; metathoracic femur length 8-8.5.

Biological Notes. *Development.* Nymphs resemble adults in form, with dorsal surface of compound eyes more prominently pointed in younger instars, becoming more tapered with age. Nymphs demonstrate the same base coloration and occasional dark mottling as adults, typically marked with a thick blackish line down median of abdominal dorsal surface. Earlier instar nymphs generally lighter and more monochromatic.

Adulthood. This species is multivoltine, having several overlapping generations occurring throughout the year. Adult males occur from early May to mid-October; adult females occur from early March to early November. Habitat includes shrubland and rocky foothills with sparse vegetation and sandy soil. Adults and nymphs are most commonly encountered actively running along the ground amid rocks or leaf litter. They are also encountered climbing through dry grasses and low-lying vegetation, occasionally found within green shrubbery.

Ethology. Adults are active at all times throughout the day. Adult males are attracted to lights at night. Adults do not demonstrate a deimatic display but rather quickly dart away with great agility in response to danger.

Diagnosis. The males of this species are diagnosable among *Litaneutria* by possessing a strongly triangular head capsule with flattened vertex lying well below the dorsal surface

of the bluntly conical compound eyes, metazona markedly constricted with pronounced supracoxal expansion, and hindwings moderately maculated with a contrasting wing spot, occasionally being faint throughout. Females are diagnosable by possessing a vertex that is slightly raised in a flattened to shallow arch above dorsal surface of sharply angulated compound eyes. This species is precinctive to the Southern California/Baja California Chaparral.

Etymology. *chaparrali* is a Latinized derivative of chaparral, meaning of or from the chaparral, referring to the unique ecoregion where this species was first documented.

***Litaneutria chaparrali* Distribution Range**

01, *Litaneutria chaparrali* adult male. Valley Center, San Diego Co, CA 07.13.17

02, *Litaneutria chaparrali* adult female. Running Springs, San Bernardino Co, CA
08.02.20

03, *Litaneutria chaparrali* nymph. Griffith Park, Los Angeles Co, CA 07.11.15

04, *Litaneutria chaparrali* nymph. San Diego, San Diego Co, CA 05.24.12

Contributing Photographers.

01, *Litaneutria chaparrali* adult male
Photographed by Ryan Andrews

02, *Litaneutria chaparrali* adult female
Photographed by Carol Blaney

03, *Litaneutria chaparrali* nymph
Photographed by James P. Bailey

04, *Litaneutria chaparrali* nymph
Photographed by Justin A. Scioli

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Lianeutria emarginata*: A, male dorsal habitus. Chaparral Wildlife Management Area, Dimmit Co, TX 05.17.93; B, female dorsal habitus. Dolan Falls, Val Verde Co, TX 06.24.94

Litaneutria emarginata Anderson, 2018

Description. Habitus relatively small for genus. General coloration of both sexes mottled brownish-gray to uniform gray, extensively stippled with darker gray and black.

Head capsule triangular with concave vertex placed significantly lower than dorsal surface of compound eyes in both sexes. Vertex bearing deep sulcus in middle. Lower frons approximately twice as wide as high, superior margin weakly arched with blunted apex. Clypeus short, trapezoidal. Antennae filiform, extending to posterior margin of pronotum in female, reaching to middle of forewings in male. Ocelli significantly reduced, grouped together in isosceles triangle configuration just above base of antennae in female, positioned closer together and much more salient in male. Compound eyes conical, with dorsal surface raised into blunted points in both sexes. Head capsule mottled with various shades of brown to light gray. Compound eyes pigmented same color as body with light brown mottling.

Pronotum slender in both sexes with moderate supracoxal dilation, supracoxal sulcus well marked. Prozona margins broadly and gradually converging in female, more narrowed and acute in male. Medial keel salient along metazona, somewhat fading into prozona. Small, raised black points asymmetrically placed along medial keel throughout its metazonal length. Female pronotum finely granulated, margins with moderate denticulation; pronotal margins unarmed in male, disc relatively smooth. Male pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.66, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.80. Female pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.34, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.29. Pronotum pigmented light brown to gray, mottled with darker brown, punctated with black. Margins of pronotum edged in light brown to gray with blackish denticulation in female or blackened calluses in male, intermittently spaced along border.

Prothoracic legs. Forecoxae shorter than pronotum. Forefemora with 4 posteroventral, 11-12 anteroventral, and 4 discoidal spines, all with dark tips. Anteroventral spines alternate in length. Tibial spur furrow positioned in proximal third of forefemora. Foretibiae with 7-9 posteroventral, 11-12 anteroventral, black-tipped spines that successively increase in length toward distal apex; tibial spur reddish-brown to blackish. Forelegs pigmented same as body color with blackish stippling throughout on both exterior and interior surfaces.

Meso/metathoracic legs slender; femoral genicular lobes spined. Metathoracic metatarsi elongated, as long as remaining segments combined. Pigmentation of legs colored same as body, base of tarsal joints darker.

Wings. Based on current knowledge, this species is solely macropterous, as no brachypterous males of *emarginata* have been found to date. Male forewings long, narrow, exposing last 3-4 abdominal tergites. Forewings tinted grayish-brown with venation pigmented brown. Female brachypterous, forewings extending midway down tergite I to base of tergite II, narrow with raised veins. Forewings predominantly colored grayish-brown with lighter gray highlights in discoidal field and at apex. Distal third occasionally crossed by darkened bar. Male hindwings faintly maculated with radiating rows of brownish tessellation against hyaline field. Sub-basal region of anal area typically adorned with circular, light brownish blotch, sharply contrasting with surrounding shading. Sub-basal spot entirely absent in some individuals. Female

hindwings project beyond forewings at repose, reaching next tergite. Hindwing apices thickened, pigmented same as forewings. Anal field lightly infumated; primary veins black, crossveins light gray. Center of anal field adorned with large, bluish-black, reflective blotch.

Abdomen. Male abdomen narrow, sides parallel, mottled golden-brown and dark brown with dark brown median. Female abdomen weakly fusiform, pigmented brownish-gray. Distal margins of abdominal tergites II-IV armed with pair of upturned, triangular-shaped protuberances along median. Tips of ventroterminal lobes of sternite VII with short, acute, hook-like extensions. Male supra-anal plate broadly rounded, carinate toward distal margin. Male cerci with thickened basal segments, acutely tapered toward end, equal to or slightly surpassing subgenital plate. Female cerci not surpassing supra-anal plate.

Measurements. (All measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 19-25; pronotum length 4-5; forewing length 17-18; prothoracic coxa length 3-3.5; prothoracic femur length 4-5; metathoracic femur length 6-7. *Female.* Body length 24; pronotum length 5.5; forewing length 4.5; prothoracic coxa length 3.5; prothoracic femur length 5.5; metathoracic femur length 7.

Biological Notes. *Development.* Nymphs resemble adults in form and coloration. Nymphs demonstrate the same base coloration and mottling as adults.

Adulthood. This species is bivoltine, with adults from spring brood being found from early May to late June. Adults from fall brood are found from early September to mid-November. Habitat includes river banks and surrounding vegetation along Rio Grande and adjacent tributaries.

References. Anderson (2019) pgs 58-61

***Litaneutria emarginata* Distribution Range**

01, *Litaneutria emarginata* adult male. Falcon State Park, Starr Co, TX 11.19.20

02, *Litaneutria emarginata* adult female. La Homa, Hidalgo Co, TX 05.09.18

03, *Litaneutria emarginata* nymph. Kickapoo Cavern State Park, Kinney Co, TX
05.15.21

Contributing Photographers.

01, *Litaneutria emarginata* adult male
Photographed by Jon McIntyre

02, *Litaneutria emarginata* adult female
Photographed by Mark Buijtendijk
URL: www.inaturalist.org/observations/12401759

03, *Litaneutria emarginata* nymph
Photographed by John Garrett

A

B

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Lianeuria littoralis*: A, male holotype dorsal habitus. Ahome, Sinaloa, MEXICO 10.17; B, male holotype ventral habitus. Ahome, Sinaloa, MEXICO 10.17

Litaneutria littoralis n. sp.

Type Material. Holotype. 1 ♂ Ahome, Sinaloa, MEXICO 10.17 AVasquez. This type is deposited within the author's private collection in Las Vegas, NV.

NOTE: Female *littoralis* are presently known only from a single photographic observation. The female description portions that have been derived from said photograph are interpretive and are not meant to be diagnostic at this time.

Description. Habitus small. General pigmentation brownish-gray, mottled with black and light brown.

Head capsule triangular with vertex placed significantly lower than dorsal surface of compound eyes. Male vertex slightly convex in middle. Lower frons approximately twice as wide as high, superior margin weakly arched with blunted apex. Clypeus short, trapezoidal. Antennae filiform, extending to middle of forewings in male, reaching pronotum in female. Ocelli small, grouped together in isosceles triangle configuration just above base of antennae. Male compound eyes conical, dorsal surface raised into blunted points. Head capsule mottled with various shades of brown, stippled with black. Vertex darker brown. Compound eyes pigmented same color as body with dark brown mottling.

Pronotum slender in male with supracoxal dilation moderately marked, supracoxal sulcus well marked. Female pronotum more robust. Male prozona margins narrow, gradually converging. Medial keel salient along metazona, somewhat fading into prozona. Metazonal margins parallel. Small, raised black points asymmetrically placed along medial keel throughout its metazonal length. Male pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.44, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.65. Pronotum pigmented light brownish-gray in both sexes, mottled with darker brown, punctated with black. Margins of pronotum intermittently spaced with blackened calluses. Prosternum with pair of black calluses on either side of median in metazonal region.

Prothoracic legs. Forecoxae shorter than pronotum. Forefemora with 4 posteroventral, 12 anteroventral, and 4 discoidal spines, all with dark tips. Anteroventral spines alternate in length. Tibial spur furrow positioned in proximal third of forefemora. Foretibiae with 9 posteroventral, 11 anteroventral, black-tipped spines that successively increase in length toward distal apex; tibial spur blackish. Forelegs pigmented somewhat lighter than body color with blackish stippling throughout on both exterior and interior surfaces. Mottling forms poorly defined bands on exterior surface of forefemora. Interior surface of forecoxae with four blackish spots lining anterior margin.

Meso/metathoracic legs slender, slightly widened at base. Femoral genicular lobes spined. Metathoracic metatarsi elongated, measuring as long as remaining segments combined. Pigmentation of legs same as body with darkened apices of femora, tibiae and each tarsal joint.

Wings. Based on current knowledge, this species is solely macropterous, as no brachypterous males of *littoralis* have been found to date. Male forewings long, narrow, covering most of abdomen, exposing only terminalia; pigmentation of male forewings tinted grayish-brown with venation pigmented brown. Female forewings shortened, elliptical, reaching abdominal tergite III; pigmentation of female forewings mottled dark

gray with distal third more blackish. Male hindwings maculated with radiating rows of brownish tessellation against hyaline field. Sub-basal region of anal area adorned with blackish blotch, sharply contrasting with surrounding shading.

Abdomen. Male abdomen narrow, sides parallel, mottled golden-brown and dark brown. Female abdomen fusiform with distal margins of tergites II-V armed with pair of upturned, triangular-shaped protuberances along median. Pigmentation dark gray, blotched with reddish-brown. Male supra-anal plate broadly rounded, carinate toward distal margin. Subgenital plate elongated. Cerci with thickened basal segments, acutely tapered toward end, equal to subgenital plate. Female supra-anal plate nearly as large as tergites VII-IX combined, rooflike with rounded corners and arched median crest.

Measurements. (All measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 27; pronotum length 5.5; forewing length 19.5; prothoracic coxa length 3.5; prothoracic femur length 5.5; metathoracic femur length 7.5.

Diagnosis. This species is diagnosable among other *Litaneutria* males by possessing a combination of characters that include the vertex significantly lowered below the dorsal surface of the bluntly conical compound eyes, hindwings with sharply contrasting blackish spot, interior surface of forecoxae with four blackish spots lining anterior margin, and prosternum with pair of black dots on either side of median in metazonal region. Additionally, supracoxal dilation is weakly to moderately marked with metazonal margins parallel. Male pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.44, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.65.

Etymology. *littoralis* is a Latin term meaning shore or coastal, referencing the Sinaloa Coastal Plain from where this species is described, and based on current knowledge, precinctive.

***Litaneutria littoralis* Distribution Range**

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Lianeutria minor*: A, macropterous male dorsal habitus. Monahans Sandhills State Park, Ward Co, TX 07.02.99; B, brachypterous male dorsal habitus. CO Route 109, MP 42, Otero Co, CO 08.11.90

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Litanentria minor*: C, female dorsal habitus. Sand Creek Massacre NHS, Kiowa Co, CO 08.28.08

Litaneutria minor (Scudder, 1872)

Description. General coloration light gray to light brown with variable degree of darker gray striations, black punctulation, and tan to brown mottling. Female individuals occasionally pigmented dark gray with extensive whitish-gray and black mottling.

Head capsule strongly triangular, wider in female. Male vertex flattened to slightly arched, placed lower than dorsal surface of compound eyes. Compound eyes narrowly ovoid, dorsal surface somewhat truncated. Vertex crossed by four shallow furrows. Female vertex slightly raised above dorsal surface of compound eyes with middle portion smoothed into shallow arch. Compound eyes narrowly rounded, dorsal surface somewhat truncated. Compound eyes pigmented same color as body with grayish-white flecks that often form lateral bands in female. Lower frons approximately twice as wide as high, superior margin broadly arched with blunted point in center. Ocelli rather small in both sexes, grouped together in tight triangle configuration just above base of antennae with unpaired median ocellus ovoid and lateral ocelli more rounded. Antennae black or brown, filiform, extending to posterior margin of pronotum in female, reaching midway down forewings in male.

Pronotum slender, elongated in male with weak supracoxal dilation. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.48, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.50. Prozona elongate, elliptical, margins sharply converging. Pronotal disc relatively smooth with lateral margins interspersed with small, blackish calluses. Female pronotum stout with weak supracoxal dilation. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.35, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.23. Prozona elliptical with gradually converging margins. Pronotal disc with sparse granulation, lateral margins denticulate. Supracoxal sulcus marked in both sexes. Medial keel distinct throughout pronotum, more salient along metazona. Coloration typically gray with variable degree of tan, reddish-brown, blackish or lighter gray blotching. Some individuals may have dark gray pronotal striations to compliment lighter pronotal blotching.

Prothoracic legs. Forecoxae slightly shorter than pronotum. Forefemora with 4-5 posteroventral, 11-14 anteroventral, and 3 discoidal spines, all with dark tips. Anteroventral spines alternate in length. Tibial spur furrow positioned in middle of forefemora. Exterior surface solid gray to tan, blotched with lighter gray to darker brown. Forefemora with dark punctulation on interior surface that may be concentrated into larger blotches toward anteroventral margin. Foretibiae with 7-9 posteroventral, 7-11 anteroventral, black-tipped spines that successively increase in length toward distal apex; tibial spur reddish-brown.

Meso/metathoracic legs slender, femora gray in middle of shaft, variably punctulated with brownish-black, with single, darkened annulation toward apices; tibiae typically shaded lighter gray. Meso/metathoracic legs occasionally brown throughout. Base of tarsal joints darker. Metathoracic metatarsi elongated, as long as remaining segments combined.

Wings. Male primarily macropterous, uncommonly co-occurring with brachypterous forms where wings are shortened as in female. Brachypterous males have forewings reaching to proximal margin of abdominal tergite II. Forewings of brachypterous males generally colored light brown, opaque. Macropterous males with narrow forewings that expose last 3-4 abdominal tergites, discoidal area weakly

infumated, subhyaline with light gray to dark gray tint. Costal area occasionally lighter, separated by darkened costal ridge. Long veins of forewings marked intermittently with dark brown, usually near insertion of cross veins. Female forewings always brachypterous, reaching midway down tergite 1, occasionally reaching into tergite II. Forewing shape elongate-oval, dark brown, tan or gray, often with darker streaks and punctulation; stigma unicolorous with background color, inconspicuous. Macropterous males have hindwings tessellate with light brown to brownish-gray radiating rows of maculations upon a hyaline field. Sub-basal region of anal area adorned with light to heavily darkened brownish-gray spot with clearly defined delimitation, contrasted against lighter background maculation. Hindwings of female and brachypterous male project slightly beyond apices of forewings, reaching to distal margin of tergite II. Exposed portion of hindwings pigmented tan to gray with black reticulation. Anal area with concentration of metallic purplish-black maculations amidst grayish-brown tessellation toward margins. Base lightly infumated with gray.

Abdomen. Male abdomen narrow, sides parallel. Coloration largely gray on dorsal surface with light brown highlights, ventral surface suffused with much more extensive light brown. Male supra-anal plate broadly rounded, carinate at base. Male cerci long, extending well past styli, cylindrical, tapering. Female abdomen broadly fusiform with distal margins of tergites II-V armed with pair of upturned, triangular-shaped protuberances along median that occasionally accompanied by pair of dark gray to blackish longitudinal lines that traverse dorsal surface. Pigmentation unicolorous gray, blotched with lighter gray, tan, or reddish-brown, rarely with blackish spotting. Female supra-anal plate nearly as large as tergites VII-IX combined, rooflike with rounded corners and arched median crest.

Measurements. (all measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 22-32; pronotum length 4-6; forewing length 16-22 (macropterous), 5-7 (brachypterous); prothoracic coxa length 3-4; prothoracic femur length 4-6; metathoracic femur length 6-8. *Female.* Body length 20-34; pronotum length 5-7.5; forewing length 4-7; prothoracic coxa length 4-6; prothoracic femur length 5-7; metathoracic femur length 7-8.

Biological Notes. *Oothecae* are rectangular with sloping sides and rounded corners, measuring 5-11 mm long, 4-6.5 mm wide, and 3-5 mm tall. Distal end with emergence area slightly extended forward to form a blunted point; proximal end rounded. Lateral surface ribbed, delimiting approximately 5-10 egg chambers. External wall light brown to gray in coloration with emergence area consisting of 8-15 closely spaced operculi placed along dorsal ridge that may be concealed by dried, excess froth. Larger oothecae may have operculi partially fused, thereby forcing nymphs to emerge from hollow point on distal end. Oothecae are attached along ventral surface. Oviposition sites generally consist of plant stems and stones approximately 1 foot above the ground.

Development. Nymph emergence occurs approximately 30 days after oviposition for spring/summer broods and up to 7 months for those oothecae that overwinter. Nymphs resemble adults in form, with dorsal surface of compound eyes more prominently pointed in younger instars, becoming more flattened and truncated with age. Nymphs demonstrate the same base colors of adults, often marked with darkened line down median of abdominal dorsal surface. Earlier instar nymphs generally darker with more contrasting mottling and annulation along antennae and meso/metathoracic legs

than later instars. Nymphs mature in approximately 3 months. Males reach adulthood before females, as they require one less molt to reach maturity.

Adulthood. This species is primarily univoltine but produces a second generation in southern parts of its range. Partial broods may also occur where nymphs emerge from summer-deposited oothecae in the fall but fail to reach maturity before the onset of frost. Adults and nymphs may be collected from late March to early December and can be moderately abundant in some areas. Habitat includes open fields and rocky ground with sparse vegetation, short grasses, sagebrush, and juniper trees. Adults and nymphs are most commonly encountered actively running along the ground or navigating across stones in short spurts. They are less often found jumping or climbing in dry grasses/weeds, shrubbery, and other low vegetation, as well as occasionally spotted resting low on tree trunks and open-faced rocks. Males may live up to 7 weeks, whereas females may persist over 5 months.

Reproduction. Copulation typically lasts for 3-4 hours. Sexual cannibalism occasionally occurs after copulation has concluded. Most males escape, however. Oviposition begins approximately 2 days over mating, otherwise, unmated females will begin oviposition 25-30 days post final eclosion. Females are capable of producing 6-10 oothecae, containing between 20-40 eggs each, over their adult life span, depositing one every 4-10 days at high levels of nutrition intake, beginning in early June and terminating in late November. Unfertilized females will begin ovipositing in late August and continue producing infertile oothecae until mid-December. Mated females may occasionally produce infertile oothecae, generally after producing several fertile ones.

Ethology. Adults are active both day and night with males being attracted to lights. Adults do not demonstrate a deimatic display but rather quickly dart away with great agility in response to danger.

Narrative. Despite several distinct species occupying the *Litaneutria* genus, most literature refers to every ground mantis found in the United States as *L. minor*. Habitat demarcations that coincide with morphological differences between the species have consistently been demonstrated, bringing new perspective and contraindications to Hebard's synonymization of this genus. As such, we now know that *L. minor* occurs only in the low elevation xeric region of the Chihuahuan Desert and open grasslands of the Great Plains and does not occur west of the Rocky Mountains.

References. Anderson (2019) pgs 62-69

***Litaneutria minor* Distribution Range**

01, *Litaneutria minor* adult male. Lynn Co, TX 10.20.17

02, *Litaneutria minor* adult male. Las Cruces, Dona Ana Co, NM 11.09.18

03, *Litaneutria minor* adult female. Austin, Travis Co, TX 10.23.16

04, *Litaneutria minor* adult female. Lometa, San Saba Co, TX 09.30.17

05, *Litaneutria minor* adult female. Collyer, Gove Co, KS 09.17.20

06, *Litaneutria minor* adult female. Dunn, Scurry Co, TX 08.20.21

07, *Litaneutria minor* nymph. Caprock Canyons State Park, Briscoe Co, TX 05.02.21

08, *Litaneutria minor* nymph. Leon Valley, Bexar Co, TX 09.07.14

09, *Litaneutria minor* nymph. Jimmy Camp Creek Park, El Paso Co, CO 07.15.17

Contributing Photographers.

01, *Litaneutria minor* adult male

Photographed by Ellen Hildebrandt

URL: www.inaturalist.org/people/ellen5

02, *Litaneutria minor* adult male.

Photographed by Joel DuBois

03, *Litaneutria minor* adult female.

Photographed by Robert Deans

04, *Litaneutria minor* adult female

Photographed by Isaac Lord

05, *Litaneutria minor* adult female

Photographed provided by Wes Zinke

URL: www.creationwings.com

06, *Litaneutria minor* adult female

Photographed provided by iNaturalist observer

URL: www.inaturalist.org/home

07, *Litaneutria minor* nymph

Photographed by crseaquist

08, *Litaneutria minor* nymph

Photographed provided by iNaturalist observer

URL: www.inaturalist.org/home

09, *Litaneutria minor* nymph

Photographed by leptim

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Litaneutria obscura*: A, male dorsal habitus. Calico Basin, Clark Co, NV 06.29.16; B, female dorsal habitus. Red Rock Canyon, Clark Co, NV 06.29.16

Litaneutria obscura Scudder, 1896 **stat. rev.**

Type Material. Neotype. 1 ♂ Twentynine Palms, San Bernardino Co, CA 05.01.66, JDRowe. This type is deposited at the California Department of Food & Agriculture Plant Pest Diagnostics Center in Sacramento, CA.

Description. Habitus small, compact. General coloration of males most often golden brown, light brown, or gray with minute stippling of darker browns and black. Female typically colored light to dark gray with darker mottling or whitish-gray blotching.

Head capsule broadly triangular, somewhat compressed, wider in female. Male vertex flat, positioned well below dorsal surface of compound eyes, crossed by four shallow furrows. Female vertex level with or raised slightly above dorsal surface of compound eyes in shallow arch. Lower frons approximately twice as wide as high, superior margin broadly arched. Ocelli very reduced in female, more salient in male, rounded, grouped together in tight triangle configuration just above base of antennae. Compound eyes prominent, protruding with rounded dorsal surface in both sexes. Compound eyes pigmented same as body color with grayish-white flecks or dark brown banding. Antennae golden-brown to black, filiform, reaching midway down forewings in male, not exceeding pronotum in female.

Pronotum shortened, relatively compact, with moderate supracoxal dilation in both sexes. Male pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.34; pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.54. Female pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.17; pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.41. Supracoxal sulcus well marked; metazona saliently keeled, becoming less distinct on prozona. Pronotal margins lined with fine ciliated tubercles in male, robustly denticulate in female. Pronotum pigmented same as body with variable scattering of very fine brownish-black punctulation on prozonal disc and along humeral curves of metazona that may form darker, longitudinal lines. Female pronotum typically darker gray with suffuse blackish punctulation, often extensively blotched with whitish-gray or, uncommonly blotched with chestnut brown.

Prothoracic legs. Forecoxae slightly longer than metazona. Forefemora armed with 3 discoidal, 4 posteroventral, and 12 anteroventral spines, all with dark tips. Anteroventral spines alternate in length. Foretibiae with 8 posteroventral and 10 anteroventral, black-tipped spines that successively increase in length toward distal apex. Tibial spur furrow positioned in middle of forefemora. Forefemora mostly of uniform coloration with body, occasionally banded. Interior surface of forefemora punctulated with black, often becoming concentrated at base of discoidal spines.

Meso/metathoracic legs slender; femoral genicular lobes spined. Legs pigmented same as body color with brownish stippling. Distal terminus of meso/metafemora with single, dark brown to blackish annulations that may be faded in light tan specimens. Metathoracic metatarsi elongated, as long as remaining segments combined. Tarsomeres of body color with darkened apices.

Wings. Males typically macropterous with forewings long, narrow, slightly shorter than abdomen, concealing all tergites but the terminalia. Forewings tinted tan to light gray, semi-transparent with darkened maculations of hindwings showing through folded forewings in repose. Large veins of forewings translucent, interspersed with darkened points throughout; jugal lobe with infumated cells as in hindwing.

Uncommonly, male individuals are brachypterous with forewings just reaching to tergite II. With this variation, forewings are of body color with major veins prominently raised with short, blackish maculations interspersed throughout as in macropterous form. Distal third entirely infumated. Female forewings always brachypterous, nearly reaching distal margin of tergite II. Forewings elongate-oval, same color as body with variable stippling along major veins. Distal third with infuscated band that is often obscured by surrounding mottling. Macropterous males with anal area of hindwings typically maculated throughout with dark brown to blackish tessellation, separated by hyaline venation, becoming clear at base. Sub-basal wing spot obscured, occasionally being entirely blackish, making the wing spot indistinguishable from surrounding background. Hindwings of females and brachypterous males project beyond apices of forewings, reaching into tergite III. Anal area largely blackish-brown with variable degree of hyaline venation, base typically hyaline.

Abdomen. Male abdomen smooth, narrow, sides parallel. Dorsal median with faint, longitudinal line that is typically lighter than body color. Female abdomen broadly fusiform, striated with wavy, darker brown bands along with double line of brownish black extending down dorsal median. Distal margins of abdominal tergites II-VI armed with pair of low, upturned, triangular-shaped protuberances along median. Female supra-anal plate ovate-rounded with prominent median keel. Male supra-anal plate large, broadly triangular with apex truncated, lateral margins straight. Cerci thickened, tapered, significantly exceeding subgenital plate and styli.

Measurements. (All measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 20-26; pronotum length 4-5; forewing length 14.5-18.5; prothoracic coxa length 3-4; prothoracic femur length 4-5; metathoracic femur length 6-7. *Female.* Body length 23-28; pronotum length 5-6.5; forewing length 5.5-7; prothoracic coxa length 3-5; prothoracic femur length 4-6; metathoracic femur length 6-8.5.

Biological Notes. *Oothecae* are trapezoidal in cross-section with ribbed, convex sides and rounded corners, measuring 6-8 mm long, 3-4 mm wide, and 3-5 mm tall. Emergence area raised, keeled, terminating in divergent, triangular-shaped flaps. This area sealed with dried froth along seam until nymph emergence. Distal end concave with apical angle prolonged into emergence area; proximal end rounded, laterally oblique. Lateral surface ribbed, delimiting approximately 9-12 egg chambers on either side. External wall pigmented light tan to brown. Oviposition sites generally consist of low-lying plant stems approximately 1 foot above the ground.

Development. Nymphs resemble adults in form, coloration, and behavior. Younger instars demonstrate heavier mottling of darker grays and greater concentration of black stippling. Older instars have same base colors of adults with very similar punctulation and striping along pronotum, forelegs, and abdomen. Nymphs may be found from mid-May to late September. Maturation requires approximately 3.5 months for nymphs to develop over a series of 6-7 molts that occur every 15-21 days, depending on nutritional intake. Final instar may continue for 34 days before final molt. Nymphs of all ages are active predators, as they run about in short spurts and scramble toward prey items in a jerky manner rather than waiting ambush style for prey to cross their path.

Adulthood. This species is bivoltine, with overlapping broods being found during the summer throughout most of its range. Adult males may be found from mid-April to late October with females being encountered from early February to mid-November. Adult males live for approximately 1 month, whereas females may live up to 5 months.

Reproduction. Unmated females may produce an infertile ootheca of roughly the same size and shape as viable ones before succumbing to age.

Ethology. Adults are active both day and night with males being attracted to lights. Adults do not demonstrate a deimatic display but rather quickly dart away with great agility in response to danger. Males may flutter between resting spots when disturbed. Gravid females often lurk among small flowering plants, where they prey upon relatively larger butterflies and other nectaring insects.

Diagnosis. Males of this species are diagnosable among *Litaneutria* by possessing a shortened, relatively robust pronotum. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.34. Pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.54. Middle of vertex placed below the dorsal surface of the prominently rounded compound eyes. Macropterous males with wing length that nearly covers the entire abdomen. Hindwings heavily darkened with an obscured wing spot, occasionally being entirely blackish, making the wing spot indistinguishable. Females are diagnosable by possessing a broadly triangular, somewhat compressed head capsule with vertex level with or raised slightly above dorsal surface of protruding compound eyes in shallow arch. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.17; pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.41. This species is precinctive to the Mojave Desert.

References. Scudder (1896) pgs 209-210; Anderson (2019) pgs 50-51

***Litaneutria obscura* Distribution Range**

01, *Litaneutria obscura* adult male. Zzyzx, San Bernardino Co, CA 04.21.18

02, *Litaneutria obscura* adult male. Linnie, Inyo Co, CA 05.28.19

03, *Litaneutria obscura* adult female. Sacatara Canyon, Kern Co, CA 08.22.15

04, *Litaneutria obscura* nymph. Chambless, San Bernardino Co, CA 04.15.21

05, *Litaneutria obscura* nymph. Mojave National Preserve, San Bernardino Co, CA
03.31.15

Contributing Photographers.

01, *Litaneutria obscura* adult male
Photographed by Jess Miller-Camp

02, *Litaneutria obscura* adult male
Photographed by Marc L.

03, *Litaneutria obscura* adult female
Photographed by James P. Bailey

04, *Litaneutria obscura* nymph
Photographed by Jeremiah Degenhardt

05, *Litaneutria obscura* nymph
Photographed by Tony Iwane

A

B

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Lianeutria ocellaris*: A, male dorsal habitus. Verde River, Maricopa Co, AZ 08.26.58; B, female dorsal habitus. Maricopa Co, AZ

Litaneutria ocularis Saussure, 1892

Description. General coloration of males most often golden brown, light brown, or gray with minute stippling of darker browns and black, occasionally with extensive lighter gray mottling and golden-brown blotching. Female are typically light to dark gray with darker mottling or whitish-gray blotching.

Head capsule triangular, wider in female. Male vertex positioned lower than dorsal surface of compound eyes, flattened to slightly concave, crossed by four shallow furrows. Female vertex level with or raised slightly above dorsal surface of compound eyes in shallow arch. Lower frons approximately twice as wide as high, superior margin with blunt point in middle. Antennae golden-brown to black, filiform, reaching midway down forewings in male, not exceeding pronotum in female. Ocelli very reduced in female, more salient in male, rounded, grouped together in tight triangle configuration just above base of antennae. Compound eyes prominently rounded with rounded dorsal surface in both sexes. Compound eyes pigmented same color as body with grayish-white flecks or dark brown mottling. Brownish pigmentation of compound eyes may concentrate in center, forming darkened line across middle that may extend above lower frons, between antennal bases. Vertex often tinted lighter shade than body color, giving head capsule a banded appearance when viewed dorsally.

Pronotum elongated, narrow with weakly marked supracoxal dilation in male, more robust in female. Male pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.37, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.53. Female pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.19, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.21. Pronotal margins denticulate in female, lined with fine ciliated tubercles in male. Prozonal margins gradually converging, supracoxal sulcus well marked. Metazona clearly keeled, becoming less distinct on prozona. Metazonal keel with 10-12 darkened points placed in alternating pattern along either side of ridge, largest of which concentrate along anterior third of metazona. Additional darkened points are placed intermittently along pronotal margin. All pronotal punctulation darker and more salient in female. Pronotum pigmented same as body color with variable scattering of very fine brownish-black punctulation on prozonal disc and along humeral curves of metazona. Oftentimes pronotum marked with darker, longitudinal lines of tan, brown, or gray that create a contrastingly lighter band down median. Female pronotum may also be dark gray with suffuse blackish punctulation, often extensively blotched with whitish-gray or chestnut brown.

Prothoracic legs. Forecoxae slightly longer than metazona, usually of uniform coloration with the body but may uncommonly be banded with darker mottling. Forefemora with 4 posteroventral, 10-12 anteroventral, and 3 discoidal spines, all with dark tips. Anteroventral spines alternate in length. Tibial spur furrow positioned in middle of forefemora. Forefemora mostly of uniform coloration, occasionally with small, brownish blotches in basal half of exterior surface or with more extensive mottling throughout basal half. Interior surface of forefemora punctulated with black, often becoming concentrated at base of discoidal spines, forming sizeable blotches. Foretibiae with 7-9 posteroventral and 7-11 anteroventral, black-tipped spines that successively increase in length toward distal apex; tibial spur reddish-brown. Tarsomeres of body color with variable pale greenish tint, darkened somewhat at apices.

Meso/metathoracic legs slender, pigmented similar to body color with brownish stippling along femora, occasionally with pale green tint on tibiae. Distal terminus of meso/metafemora with single, dark brown to blackish annulations that may be faded in light tan specimens. Femoral genicular lobes spined. Metathoracic metatarsi elongated, as long as remaining segments combined.

Wings. Based on current knowledge, this species is solely macropterous, as no brachypterous males of *ocularis* have been found to date. Male forewings long, narrow, shorter than abdomen, exposing last 2-4 abdominal tergites. Forewings shaded same coloration as body. Large veins of forewings translucent with tint of body color, interspersed with darkened points throughout; jugal lobe with infumated cells as in hindwing. Costal ridge may be whitish, outlined with body color. Female brachypterous, elongate-oval, nearly reaching distal margin of tergite II. Forewings pigmented same color as body with variable stippling along major veins. Distal third with infuscated band that is often obscured by surrounding mottling. Ventral surface of forewings with darkened blotch toward apices that shows through membrane and is seen as an obfuscated, muted maculation on dorsal. Male hindwings as long as or slightly shorter than forewings. Anal area maculated throughout with light to moderate brownish tessellation, separated by hyaline venation. Sub-basal portion of hindwings with large, light to heavily darkened spot. Delimitation of hindwing spot clearly defined, contrasted against lighter surrounding maculation. Female hindwings project 2 mm beyond apices of forewings, reaching into tergite III. Opaque apices can often be seen through exposed portion of hindwings when folded at rest beneath forewings. Anal area largely blackish-brown with variably degree of hyaline venation, base typically hyaline.

Abdomen. Male abdomen smooth, narrow, sides parallel. Dorsal median with faint, longitudinal line that is typically lighter than body color. Distal margins of each tergite with pair of black points straddling dorsal median. Female abdomen broadly fusiform, striated with wavy, darker brown bands along with double line of brownish black extending down dorsal median. Distal margins of abdominal tergites II-VI armed with pair of low, upturned, triangular-shaped protuberances along median. Female supra-anal plate ovate-rounded with prominent median keel. Male supra-anal plate large, broadly triangular with apex truncated, lateral margins straight. Cerci thickened, tapered, significantly exceeding subgenital plate and styli.

Measurements. (All measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 22-32; pronotum length 4-6; forewing length 14.5-22; prothoracic coxa length 3-5; prothoracic femur length 4-6; metathoracic femur length 6-8. *Female.* Body length 24-33; pronotum length 5-7; forewing length 4-7; prothoracic coxa length 3-4.5; prothoracic femur length 5-6; metathoracic femur length 7-8.

Biological Notes. *Oothecae* are trapezoidal in cross-section with ribbed, convex sides and rounded corners, measuring 7-8 mm long, 4-5 mm wide, and 4-5 mm tall. Emergence area raised, keeled, terminating in divergent, triangular-shaped flaps. This area sealed with dried froth along seam until nymph emergence. Distal end concave with apical angle prolonged into emergence area; proximal end rounded, laterally oblique. Lateral surface ribbed, delimiting approximately 10-12 egg chambers on either side. External wall pigmented light tan to brown. Oviposition sites generally consist of low-lying plant stems approximately 1 foot above the ground.

Development. Nymphs resemble adults in form, coloration, and behavior. Younger instars demonstrate heavier mottling of darker grays and greater concentration of black stippling. Older instars have same base colors of adults with very similar punctulation and striping along pronotum, forelegs, and abdomen. Nymphs may be found from early March to mid-December.

Adulthood. This species is multivoltine, with overlapping broods occurring throughout most of its range. Adult of both sexes may be found from late February to mid-November. Adults are most commonly encountered actively darting in short spurts along bare ground, climbing across open stones, or scurrying between desert shrubberies. They also climb low-lying vegetation and rocks and may be found perched atop various natural obstacles.

Ethology. Adults are active both day and night with males being attracted to lights. Adults do not demonstrate a deimatic display but rather quickly dart away with great agility in response to danger.

References. Anderson (2019) pgs 70-78

***Litaneutria ocularis* Distribution Range**

01, *Litaneutria ocularis* adult male. Vail, Pima Co, AZ 06.17.05

02, *Litaneutria ocularis* adult male. Los Cabos, Baja California Sur, MEXICO 10.18.18

03, *Litaneutria ocularis* adult female. Vail, Pima Co, AZ 11.19.06

04, *Litaneutria ocularis* adult female. Los Cabos, Baja California Sur, MEXICO 10.20.18

05, *Litaneutria ocularis* nymph. Mexicali, Baja California, MEXICO 04.18.18

06, *Litaneutria ocularis* ootheca.

Contributing Photographers.

01, *Litaneutria ocularis* adult male
Photographed by Jillian Cowles

02, *Litaneutria ocularis* adult male
Photographed by Christian F. Schwarz – Biodiversiphile.com

03, *Litaneutria ocularis* adult female
Photographed by Jillian Cowles

04, *Litaneutria ocularis* adult female
Photographed by Justyn T. Stahl

05, *Litaneutria ocularis* nymph
Photographed by Hector Daniel Pinto Santana

06, *Litaneutria ocularis* ootheca
Photographed by Yen Saw

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Litaneutria pacifica*: A, male neotype dorsal habitus. Hat Creek, Shasta Co, CA 08.23.64; B, female dorsal habitus. Redding, Shasta Co, CA 08.23.84

Litaneutria pacifica Scudder, 1896

Type Material. Neotype. 1 ♂ Hat Creek, Shasta Co, CA 08.23.64. This type is deposited at the California Department of Food & Agriculture Plant Pest Diagnostics Center in Sacramento, CA.

Description. Habitus small. General coloration of both sexes light gray, tan, or brown with variable degree of darker striations, black punctulation, and tan to gray mottling. Female coloration much more variable than male.

Head capsule wide, strongly triangular, wider in female. Male vertex placed below dorsal surface of compound eyes, flattened to slightly arched, crossed by four shallow furrows, often with darker band between compound eyes. Female vertex raised well above dorsal surface of compound eyes, broadly arched in middle. Lower frons approximately twice as wide as high, superior margin broadly arched. Ocelli reduced in female, more salient in male. Male compound eyes pronounced, narrowly ovoid, dorsal surface truncated. Female compound eyes narrowed, dorsal surface narrowly rounded, occasionally with slight angulation. Antennae black or brown, filiform, extending to posterior margin of pronotum in female, reaching midway down forewings in male. Pigmentation of head capsule typically mottled gray, occasionally with tan to reddish-brown highlights. Compound eyes same color as body with grayish-white flecks.

Pronotum fairly elongated, supracoxal dilation pronounced. Prozona somewhat extended, margins strongly converging; metazona somewhat constricted in male. Male pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.42; pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.66. Female pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.24; pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.36. Medial keel distinct with raised, asymmetrically placed black points along metazona portion, more pronounced in female. Supracoxal sulcus evident. Pronotal disc relatively smooth, lateral margins lined with fine ciliated tubercles in male, interspersed by stout denticulation in female. Pigmentation of pronotum typically gray with variable degree of opposing tan to reddish-brown highlights or entirely tan. Some individuals may have dark gray or brown pronotal striations to compliment lighter pronotal coloration.

Prothoracic legs. Forecoxae slightly shorter than pronotum. Forefemora with 3 discoidal, 3 posteroventral, and 11-12 anteroventral spines, all with dark tips. Anteroventral spines alternate in length. Foretibiae with 8 posteroventral, 11 anteroventral, black-tipped spines that successively increase in length toward distal apex. Tibial spur furrow positioned in middle of forefemora. Exterior surface of forelegs pigmented solid gray to tan, blotched with lighter gray to darker tan. Forefemora with dark punctulation on interior surface that may be concentrated into larger blotches toward anteroventral margin. Tibial spur reddish-brown.

Meso/metathoracic legs slender, typically shaded gray to brown, variably punctulated with brownish-black, with darkened region toward apices. Meso/metathoracic legs may be pigmented tan throughout in light phase or, uncommonly, light tan in dark phase. Base of tarsal joints darkened. Metathoracic metatarsi elongated, as long as remaining segments combined.

Wings. Males typically macropterous with forewings long, narrow, concealing most of abdomen, exposing terminalia. Macropterous males have weakly infumated, subhyaline forewings with light gray to dark gray tint. Costal area occasionally lighter, separated by darkened costal ridge. Long veins marked intermittently with dark brown, usually near insertion of cross veins. Uncommonly, male individuals are brachypterous with forewings just reaching to proximal margin of abdominal tergite II. With this variation, forewings are generally pigmented light brown, opaque. Female forewings always brachypterous, reaching midway down tergite I, occasionally reaching into tergite II. Forewing shape elongate-oval with raised venation. Forewings pigmented tan or gray, often with darker streaks and darkened distal third. Macropterous males have hindwings lightly tessellate with radiating rows of faint grayish-brown maculations upon a lighter gray to hyaline field. Sub-basal portion of anal area adorned with light fuscous spot, weakly contrasting with surrounding shading. Hindwing spot typically round but may be oblique, reduced, or entirely absent. Female and brachypterous male hindwings project slightly beyond apices of forewings, reaching to distal margin of tergite II. Exposed portion of hindwings may be highlighted with tan, otherwise gray.

Abdomen. Male abdomen narrow, sides parallel. Coloration largely gray on dorsal surface with light brown highlights, ventral surface suffused with much more extensive light brown. Some macropterous individuals may have terminalia and last 2-4 exposed abdominal tergites colored light tan, greatly contrasting against otherwise gray-toned body. Male supra-anal plate broadly rounded, carinate at base. Male cerci long, extending well past styli, cylindrical, tapering. Female abdomen broadly fusiform with distal margins of tergites II-V armed with pair of upturned, triangular-shaped protuberances along median that occasionally accompanied by pair of dark gray to blackish longitudinal lines that traverses dorsal surface. Pigmentation gray or tan, streaked with lighter gray to darker tan, or blotched with reddish-brown to tan. Female supra-anal plate nearly as large as tergites VII-IX combined, rooflike with rounded corners and arched median crest.

Measurements. (all measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 22-30; pronotum length 4-6; forewing length 16-20; prothoracic coxa length 3-4; prothoracic femur length 4-6; metathoracic femur length 6-7. *Female.* Body length 24-31; pronotum length 5-7; forewing length 4-6; prothoracic coxa length 3-4; prothoracic femur length 5-6; metathoracic femur length 7-8.

Biological Notes. *Development.* Nymphs resemble adults in form, with dorsal surface of compound eyes more prominently pointed in younger instars, becoming more flattened and truncated with age. Nymphs demonstrate the same base colors of adults, often with darkened line down median of abdominal dorsal surface. Earlier instar nymphs generally darker with more contrasting mottling and annulations along antennae and meso/metathoracic legs than later instars.

Adulthood. This species is primarily univoltine but has second generation in southern parts of its range. Adults and nymphs may be collected from late March to early December. Habitat includes open fields and rocky ground with sparse vegetation. Adults and nymphs are most commonly encountered running along the ground in short spurts or climbing in dry grasses/weeds, shrubbery, and other low vegetation.

References. Anderson (2019) pgs 78-84

***Litaneutria pacifica* Distribution Range**

01, *Litaneutria pacifica* adult male. San Emidio, Kern Co, CA 07.06.19

02, *Litaneutria pacifica* adult female. Red Bluff, Tehama Co, CA 09.23.13

03, *Litaneutria pacifica* adult female. Ramona Grasslands, San Diego Co, CA 08.01.21

Contributing Photographers.

01, *Litaneutria pacifica* adult male
Photographed by James P. Bailey

02, *Litaneutria pacifica* adult female
Photographed by Rob Irwin

03, *Litaneutria pacifica* adult female
Photographed by James P. Bailey

A

B

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Litanentria scopulosa*: A, male holotype dorsal habitus. Apache Junction, Pinal Co, AZ 03.20.96; B, male paratype dorsal habitus. NPS Headquarters area, Mesa Co, CO 07.30.62

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Titanentria scopulosa*: C, female allotype dorsal habitus. Grand Junction, Mesa Co, CO 07.13.54

Litaneutria scopulosa n. sp.

Type Material. Holotype. 1 ♂ Apache Junction, Pinal Co, AZ 03.20.96, KKAnderson. **Allotype.** 1 ♀ Grand Junction, Mesa Co, CO 07.13.54, AHBarnum. **Paratypes.** 1 ♂ NPS Headquarters area, Mesa Co, CO 07.30.62, McCoy; 1 ♂ Little Egypt, Garfield Co, UT 08.23.84, NBaumann; 1 ♀ Little Egypt, Garfield Co, UT 08.23.84, NBaumann. All type material is deposited within the author's private collection in Las Vegas, NV.

Description. Habitus fairly small. General coloration of both sexes mottled brownish-gray to uniform tan, extensively stippled with darker gray and black in dark phase, occasionally with light brown highlights along extremities of thorax and abdominal segments.

Head capsule triangular, rather robust, spanning significantly wider than pronotum. Female vertex flattened to slightly arched; middle of vertex level with or raised slightly higher than dorsal surface of compound eyes. Male vertex flattened, placed significantly lower than dorsal surface of compound eyes. Vertex bearing deep sulcus in juxtaocular region and a pair of shallow furrows near center. Lower frons approximately twice as wide as high, superior margin broadly arched with acute apex. Clypeus large, trapezoidal. Antennae filiform, extending to posterior margin of pronotum in female, reaching to middle of forewings in male. Ocelli grouped together in tight triangle configuration just above base of antennae, significantly reduced in both sexes. Compound eyes large, somewhat narrowed, with dorsal surface evenly rounded in female. Male compound eyes prominently bulging, rising above vertex, with dorsal surface evenly rounded. Compound eyes pigmented same color as body with dark brown mottling.

Pronotum robust with supracoxal dilation broadened, pronounced in both sexes. Prozona elongated, margins moderately converging in male, more gradual in female; supracoxal sulcus well marked in both sexes. Medial keel distinct along metazona, somewhat fading into prozona. Raised black points asymmetrically placed along medial keel throughout its metazonal length, these points more salient in female. Pronotal margins lightly denticulate in male, disc relatively smooth. Margins heavily denticulate with stout teeth in female, pronotal disc moderately granulated. Male pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.27, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.47. Female pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.17, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.16. Pronotum pigmented tan or mottled grayish-brown, punctated with black and occasionally edged in light brown. Tan phase males uncommonly have darker brown, contoured striations along inner curvature of metazona.

Prothoracic legs. Forecoxae slightly shorter than pronotum. Forefemora with 4 posteroventral, 11-12 anteroventral, and 3 discoidal spines, all with dark tips. Anteroventral spines alternate in length. Tibial spur furrow positioned in middle of forefemora. Foretibiae with 8 posteroventral, 11 anteroventral, black-tipped spines that successively increase in length toward distal apex; tibial spur reddish-brown to blackish. Forelegs pigmented same as body color with blackish stippling throughout on both exterior and interior surfaces. Forefemora and forecoxae occasionally with 2-3 faint bands of darker gray coloration.

Meso/metathoracic legs slender, colored same as body, becoming darker toward femoral apices. Femoral genicular lobes spined. Base of tarsal joints darker. Metathoracic metatarsi elongated, as long as remaining segments combined.

Wings. Males typically brachypterous, with forewings reaching to proximal margin of abdominal tergite II, as in female. Macropterous males uncommon, having long, narrow forewings, exposing last 4-5 abdominal tergites. Forewings of brachypterous males generally colored light gray with major veins blackish, apices darker gray to blackish. Macropterous males have forewings tinted same coloration as body with minute, darker maculation interspersed throughout and venation pigmented whitish to hyaline. Female brachypterous, forewings extending midway down tergite I, elongate-oval with raised veins. Forewings predominantly dark gray with lighter gray shading toward costal area. Distal third darkened. Macropterous males with anal area of hindwings tessellated with light brown maculations upon hyaline field. Maculations are more rectangular-shaped along discoidal area, becoming more elongated within anal area, creating radiating bands that are interrupted by hyaline streaks. Extreme base becoming clear. Sub-basal region of anal area adorned with trapezoidal-shaped, brownish-colored spot, contrasted against surrounding lighter maculation. Brachypterous males have hindwings entirely infumated with hyaline crossveins, apices dark gray to blackish. Female hindwings project beyond forewings at repose, reaching next tergite. Hindwing apices thickened, pigmented same as forewings. Anal field infumated throughout; primary veins black, crossveins hyaline. Center of anal field adorned with large, bluish-black, reflective blotch.

Abdomen. Male abdomen narrow, sides parallel, typically colored tan to brownish with somewhat darker bands along distal portion of each tergite. Abdomen may also be predominantly gray in darker phase with lighter brown highlights. Female abdomen elongated, not fusiform as in other members of the genus. Distal margins of abdominal tergites II-V armed with pair of upturned, triangular-shaped protuberances along median. Tips of ventroterminal lobes of sternite VII with short, blunted, hook-like extensions. Male supra-anal plate broadly rounded, carinate toward distal margin. Male cerci long, significantly surpassing subgenital plate and styli. Female cerci surpassing supra-anal plate.

Measurements. (All measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 23-31.5; pronotum length 5.5-6.5; forewing length 17-21.5 (macropterous), 5-5.5 (brachypterous); prothoracic coxa length 3.5-4; prothoracic femur length 4.5-5.5; metathoracic femur length 6.5-8. *Female.* Body length 26.5-33; pronotum length 6-7.5; forewing length 6-8; prothoracic coxa length 4-4.5; prothoracic femur length 5.5-6; metathoracic femur length 8.

Biological Notes. *Oothecae* are ovoid in shape, nearly triangular in cross-section, measuring 6-9 mm long, 5-5.5 mm wide, and 3-3.5 mm tall. Distal end slightly concave with emergence area extended forward to form a blunted point; proximal end rounded. Lateral surface ribbed, delimiting approximately 5-10 egg chambers. External wall colored yellowish-gray, becoming darker toward dorsal surface. Oothecae are attached along ventral surface.

Adulthood. This species is bivoltine, with adults from spring brood being found from early April to late May. Adult males from fall brood are found from late July to early September. Adult females live longer than males and may be collected from late

June through late September throughout much of their range. Habitat includes xeric shrublands and desert mountain hillsides and meadows.

Ethology. Adults are active throughout the day with both macropterous and brachypterous males being attracted to lights at night.

Diagnosis. The males of this species are diagnosable among *Litaneutria* by possessing a flattened vertex placed well below the dorsal surface of the globular, protruding compound eyes. Pronotum broadened with lightly denticulate margin. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.27, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.47. Macropterous males have very elongated hindwings with a reduced, but clearly defined and contrasting spot. Females are diagnosable by possessing a flattened to slightly arched vertex that rises slightly above dorsal surface of broadly rounded compound eyes. Pronotum broadened with heavily denticulate margin and pronounced supracoxal dilation. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.17, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.16. This species occurs within high elevation cold desert regions throughout the Colorado Plateau and Southern Rockies.

Etymology. *scopulosa* is a Latin term meaning rocky, referencing the Colorado Plateau and Southern Rockies region within the Rocky Mountains from where this species is described, and based on current knowledge, precinctive.

***Litaneutria scopulosa* Distribution Range**

01, *Litaneutria scopolosa* adult female. Escalante National Monument, Garfield Co, UT
08.08.09

02, *Litaneutria scopolosa* nymph. Hurricane, Washington Co, UT 05.16.21

Contributing Photographers.

01, *Litaneutria scopulosa* adult female

Photographed by Jeff Mitton

mitton@colorado.edu

02, *Litaneutria scopulosa* nymph

Photographed by Chalon Boesel

Instagram: @chalonswildlife

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Litanentria skinneri*: A, male dorsal habitus. Nogales, Santa Cruz Co, AZ 09.04.68

Litaneutria skinneri Rehn, 1907

Description. Habitus small, somewhat robust for genus. Pigmentation light tan, brown, or gray, often with wash of reddish-brown on abdomen and head. Body extensively stippled with darker brown, beige, or dark gray.

Head capsule broadly triangular, somewhat compressed in male, more compact in female. Male vertex level with or arched slightly above dorsal surface of compound eyes. Female vertex raised in high arch above dorsal surface of compound eyes. Lower frons approximately twice as wide as high, roughly rectangular-shaped with sinuate superior margin. Clypeus broad. Ocelli rather small in both sexes. Compound eyes large, ovoid in male, dorsal surface rounded. Female compound eyes narrowly ovoid, dorsal surface broadly rounded. Antennae filiform, slightly exceeding posteromedial margin of pronotum in female, twice as long as pronotum in male. Base of antennae occasionally marked with obscure, blackish median bar that extends into compound eyes.

Pronotum fairly slender in male, more robust in female. Both sexes with broadly rounded supracoxal dilation, prozonal margins sharply converging. Male pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.46, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.83. Female pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.14, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.33. Medial keel of pronotum distinct on metazona, often with series of raised, blackish tubercles, transitioning into lower, longitudinal ridge on prozona. Supracoxal sulcus deep, salient. Lateral pronotal margins lightly denticulate in male with larger teeth darkened at point of insertion; margins with more pronounced, stout denticulation in female, often blackish. Pronotal pigmentation most often monochromatic but occasionally striped or mottled with contrasting shades of body color.

Prothoracic legs pigmented same as body. Forecoxae slightly shorter than pronotum with 4-5 low, darkened tubercles lining base of anteroventral margin. Forefemora about equal to pronotum in length, quite robust in female, often imperfectly banded with beige. Forefemora with 4 posteroventral, 10-14 anteroventral, and 3-4 lengthy discoidal spines, all with black tips. Anteroventral spines alternate in length. Tibial spur furrow positioned in middle of forefemora. Foretibiae with 7-11 posteroventral, 7-11 anteroventral, black-tipped spines that successively increase in length toward distal apex; tibial spur reddish-brown.

Meso/metathoracic legs slender, same color as body with darker brown stippling along shaft and darker brown annulations toward apices. Femoral genicular lobes spined. Meso/metathoracic tibiae with series of darker brown annulations, often quite faded and indistinct. Metathoracic metatarsi elongated, as long as remaining segments combined.

Wings. Males typically macropterous with forewings long, narrow, exposing last 2-4 abdominal tergites. Uncommonly, male individuals are brachypterous with forewings reaching to middle of abdominal tergite II. Forewings of macropterous males semi-hyaline, shaded same color as body, with major venation translucent, tinted with body color, marked intermittently with dark brown, usually near insertion of cross veins. Forewings of brachypterous males are elongate-ovate in shape, apices rounded with major veins raised, distinct. Pigmentation generally grayish-tan with major veins stippled with blackish. Distal third often marked with an obscure, transverse blackish maculation. Female always brachypterous with forewings extending to distal margin of tergite I, elongate-ovate in shape with raised veins. Forewings shaded same as body color with

darkened points placed intermittently along major veins and having an obscure, transverse blackish maculation in distal third. Macropterous males have hindwings quite long and broadly expanded, slightly longer than forewings. Anal area moderately maculated throughout with brownish tessellation, separated by hyaline venation. Sub-basal portion of hindwings with large, heavily darkened spot. Delimitation of hindwing spot clearly defined, deeply contrasted against lighter surrounding maculation. Female and brachypterous male hindwings project beyond apices of forewings, reaching midway into tergite II. Anal field of hindwings heavily infumated with large, darkened tessellation, major veins black, apices same coloration as forewings.

Abdomen. Male abdomen narrow, sides parallel with distinct, longitudinal carina that extend entire length. Female abdomen broadly fusiform. Distal margins of abdominal tergites II-V armed with pair of upturned, triangular-shaped protuberances along median. Dorsal median typically with alternating, longitudinal bands of various shades of gray or brown. Supra-anal plate of male squares with subtruncate apex. Cerci thickened at base, tapering toward apices, exceeding supra-anal plate but just reaching terminus of subgenital plate, not extending beyond. Styli very short. Female supra-anal plate similar to male but more elongated, cerci as long as or slightly exceeding supra-anal plate. Female subgenital plate with apical cleft not quite reaching to middle of plate.

Measurements. (All measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 22-31; pronotum length 5-6; forewing length 24-25 (macropterous), 5-7 (brachypterous); prothoracic coxa length 3-5; prothoracic femur length 4.5-6; metathoracic femur length 6-9. *Female.* Body length 22-29.5; pronotum length 4.5-7; forewing length 5.5-8; prothoracic coxa length 3-5; prothoracic femur length 5-7; metathoracic femur length 7-8.

Biological Notes. *Development.* Nymph emergence is extended over several days, with 5-6 nymphs emerging each day in consecutive waves. Nymphs resemble adults in form and pigmentation, being brownish-gray in coloration with light brown mottling.

Adulthood. This species is univoltine throughout much of its range and bivoltine toward the more southern portion of its distribution. Adult males are generally found from early May to late August. Females are encountered from early July until late October. A spring brood occurs in March where the generations overlap. Both sexes are most commonly discovered actively running along the open ground in short spurts. They are less often found jumping or climbing through dry grasses, low vegetation, or observed resting upon bare faces of large rocks.

Ethology. Adults are active both day and night with males being attracted to lights. Adults do not demonstrate a deimatic display but rather quickly dart away with great agility in response to danger.

References. Anderson (2019) pgs 85-90

***Litaneutria skinneri* Distribution Range**

01, *Litaneutria skinneri* adult male. Pena Blanca Lake, Santa Cruz Co, AZ 08.24.17

02, *Litaneutria skinneri* adult male. Moab, Grand Co, UT 07.23.17

03, *Litaneutria skinneri* adult female. Kohls Ranch, Gila Co, AZ 09.05.13

04, *Litaneutria skinneri* nymph. Rio Rancho, Sandoval Co, NM 08.04.21

Contributing Photographers.

01, *Litaneutria skinneri* adult male
Photographed by James P. Bailey

02, *Litaneutria skinneri* adult male
Photographed by Pam Piombino

03, *Litaneutria skinneri* adult female
Photographed by Carla H. Kishinami

04, *Litaneutria skinneri* nymph
Photographed by Brandon Bourassa, Department of Herpetology, ABQ Biopark

Voucher Specimen Photographs. *Litaneutria superna*: A, male holotype dorsal habitus. Cambridge, Valley Co, ID 08.20.70

Litaneutria superna n. sp.

Type Material. Holotype. 1 ♂ Cambridge, Valley Co, ID 08.20.70. Type specimen is deposited within the author's private collection in Las Vegas, NV.

Description. Habitus rather large, robust for genus. General pigmentation of both sexes brownish-gray to light brown.

Head capsule triangular, spanning significantly wider than pronotum. Male vertex placed lower than dorsal surface of compound eyes, undulate to flattened in middle. Female vertex level with or raised slightly above dorsal surface of compound eyes in shallow to undulated arch. Lower frons approximately twice as wide as high, superior margin with acute apex. Clypeus trapezoidal. Antennae filiform, extending to posterior margin of pronotum in female, reaching to middle of forewings in male. Ocelli grouped together in tight triangle configuration just above base of antennae, significantly reduced in female, more salient in female. Male compound eyes narrowly ovoid with dorsal surface rounded. Female compound eyes protruding, dorsal surface broadly rounded. Compound eyes pigmented same color as body with dark brown mottling.

Pronotum shortened, relatively robust with broadly rounded supracoxal dilation in male, more robust with supracoxal dilation indistinct in female. Male pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.35, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.37. Female pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.30, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.15. Medial keel distinct along metazona, somewhat fading into prozona. Pronotal margins unarmed in male, disc relatively smooth. Margins denticulate in female, pronotal disc sparsely granulated. Pronotum pigmented brownish-gray to light brown, mottled with darker browns.

Prothoracic legs. Forecoxae slightly shorter than pronotum. Forefemora with 4 posteroventral, 13 anteroventral, and 4 discoidal spines, all with dark tips. Anteroventral spines alternate in length. Tibial spur furrow positioned in middle of forefemora. Foretibiae with 9 posteroventral, 11 anteroventral, black-tipped spines that successively increase in length toward distal apex. Forelegs pigmented same as body color.

Meso/metathoracic legs slender, pigmented same as body, becoming darker toward femoral and tibial apices. Femoral genicular lobes spined. Base of tarsal joints darker. Metathoracic metatarsi elongated, as long as remaining segments combined.

Wings. Males may either be macropterous or brachypterous with both forms seemingly co-occurring in equal numbers. Macropterous males have long, narrow forewings, exposing last 4-5 abdominal tergites. Pigmentation of forewings tinted same color as body with minute, darker maculation interspersed throughout cells. Brachypterous males have forewings reaching to proximal margin of abdominal tergite II, as in female. Forewings of brachypterous males generally colored gray to light brown with major veins blackish, apices darker gray to blackish. Female brachypterous, forewings extending midway down tergite I, elongate-oval with raised veins. Forewings predominantly dark gray. Distal third darkened. Macropterous males with anal area of hindwings very lightly tessellated with faint brownish maculations upon hyaline field. Sub-basal region of anal area adorned with small, brownish-colored spot, contrasted against much lighter surrounding maculation, delimitation of hindwing spot clearly defined. Female and brachypterous male hindwings project beyond forewings at repose,

reaching next tergite. Hindwing apices thickened, pigmented same as forewings. Anal field infumated throughout, primary veins black, crossveins hyaline.

Abdomen. Male abdomen rather stocky, sides parallel, pigmented in brownish tones. Female abdomen fusiform. Distal margins of abdominal tergites II-V armed with pair of upturned, triangular-shaped protuberances along median. Male supra-anal plate broadly rounded, carinate toward distal margin. Male cerci long, significantly surpassing subgenital plate and styli. Female cerci surpassing supra-anal plate.

Measurements. (All measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 28.5-29; pronotum length 5-5.5; forewing length 19.5-20 (macropterous), 5-5.5 (brachypterous); prothoracic coxa length 4.5-5; prothoracic femur length 5.5-6; metathoracic femur length 7.5-8. *Female.* Body length 29-31; pronotum length 6-6.5; forewing length 5.5-6; prothoracic coxa length 4.5-5; prothoracic femur length 5.5-6; metathoracic femur length 8-8.5.

Biological Notes. *Adulthood.* This species is univoltine. Adults may be encountered from mid-July to mid-September. Habitat includes rocky hillsides and alpine meadows.

Diagnosis. The males of this species are diagnosable among *Litaneutria* by possessing a vertex placed well below dorsal surface of the narrowly ovoid compound eyes. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.35, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.37. Macropterous males have short/narrow hindwings that are lightly maculated throughout with a small but clearly defined and highly contrasting wing spot. Females are diagnosable by possessing a vertex raised slightly above dorsal surface of the broadly rounded compound eyes in shallow to undulated arch. Pronotum robust with indistinct supracoxal dilation. Pronotal length to supracoxal dilation width 2.30, pronotal length to minimal metazonal width 3.15. This species is precinctive to the Columbia Plateau, Blue Mountains and Okanogan Plateau ecoregions of the Pacific Northwest.

Etymology. *superna* is a Latin term meaning upper, above, or northern—referencing the furthest known reaches of positive latitude that this species occupies among *Litaneutria*.

Litaneutria superna Distribution Range

01, *Litaneutria superna* adult male. Ellensburg, Kittitas Co, WA 08.16.17

01, *Litaneutria superna* nymph. Quincy, Chelan Co, WA 07.08.19

Contributing Photographers.

01, *Litaneutria superna* adult male
Photographed by Merrill A. Peterson

01, *Litaneutria superna* nymph
Photographed by Philipp Wickey

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